

Search Strategy & Search Mechanisms of Academic databases

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Search Strategy

Finding relevant and high-quality results while conducting any search, especially in academic databases, requires a well-structured search technique. This is a detailed guide to assist you in creating a successful search strategy:

1. Defining research question or topic
 - Analyse your research question: Determine the essential terms and concepts. For instance, if "What is the impact of artificial intelligence on healthcare?" is your research question, "Healthcare," "impact," and "artificial intelligence" could be some of your main ideas.
 - Make use of similar phrases and synonyms: Consider different words or modifications for your main ideas. For example:
 - Artificial Intelligence = AI, machine learning, deep learning
 - Healthcare = medicine, health systems, clinical care
2. Choosing the Right Database
 - Interdisciplinary databases: Google Scholar, Dimensions AI (good for a broad range of topics)
 - Discipline-specific databases: PubMed (healthcare), JSTOR (humanities and social sciences), LISA (library and information sciences)
 - Open Access Repositories: CORE, DOAJ (for free-to-access articles)
3. Starting with a Broad Search
 - Initial broad search: Begin by entering a combination of your key concepts, without too many restrictions. This helps you get a sense of the literature available on your topic.

For example, in Google Scholar, you might start with:

- “artificial intelligence” healthcare

Similarly, in PubMed, you might start with:

- “artificial intelligence” AND healthcare

- Use Boolean operators: Begin with simple Boolean combinations (AND, OR, NOT). These operators allow you to broaden or narrow the search:
 - AND: Narrows the search (results must include both terms). E.g., “artificial intelligence” AND healthcare.
 - OR: Broadens the search (results may include either term). E.g., “artificial intelligence” OR AI.
 - NOT: Excludes terms. E.g., “artificial intelligence” NOT “robotics”.

4. Reviewing and refining results
 - Examine titles and abstracts
 - Look for common terms
 - Narrowing by date

- Narrowing by article type
 - Use database-specific filters
5. Use Advanced Search Features
 - Field searching: Specify which fields you want to search (title, abstract, keywords, etc.). For example, in PubMed, you can search within the “title/abstract” or “MeSH terms” (Medical Subject Headings).
 - Phrase searching: Use quotation marks for exact phrases (e.g., “machine learning”).
 - Truncation and wildcards: Use an asterisk (*) or other symbols to search for variations of a word (e.g., health retrieves health, healthcare, healthiness).
 6. Analysing and Extracting Relevant Information
 - Citations: Identify important papers and authors in the field. Check the citations and references in these papers for additional sources.
 - Related articles: Many databases offer a “related articles” feature that can help you find similar studies.
 - Key findings: Focus on the abstracts, methods, results, and conclusions of the articles to understand the scope and relevance to your research.
 7. Organizing and Managing Results
 - Use a reference manager: Tools like Zotero, EndNote, or Mendeley can help you organize and cite your sources efficiently.
 - Save important articles: Most databases allow you to save articles, mark them as favourites, or email them to yourself.
 8. Iterating and Modifying Search
 - Adjust keywords: Based on the articles reviewed, consider expanding or refining the keywords to explore different aspects of the specific topic.
 - Explore related fields: Try looking at specialized databases (such as ERIC for themes linked to education or LISA for library sciences) if the particular topic crosses over into other fields.
 9. Setting Alerts for Ongoing Research
 - Setting up email alerts based on terms searched is an option with many databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, and Dimensions AI.
 - Keeping up with the most recent findings in that field is made easier using this feature.
 10. Reviewing Citations and Citations Analysis (If Available)
 - Citation analysis: The number of citations can be found in certain databases (such as Dimensions AI and Google Scholar), which indicates the significance of a publication in the area.
 - Lists of references: To locate more sources that might not have come up in that search, look through the reference lists of pertinent publications.

Search Mechanisms

In order to navigate academic databases more effectively and precisely, search mechanisms are essential tools. By enhancing, expanding, or filtering search results, these tools make sure that only the best and most pertinent data is returned. Finding scholarly literature is made easier and more efficient with the use of sophisticated features including citation analysis, Boolean operators, truncation, and phrase searches.

These search features enable searches to be customized to particular needs in a variety of academic databases, including Google scholar, PubMed, JStor, Dimensions AI, LISA, DOAJ, OATD, and CORE, limiting information overload and minimizing irrelevant results. By using these tools, researchers may do a more thorough literature review, ensuring that important papers are located and keeping abreast of the most recent advancements in the field.

Analysis of Search Strategies and Mechanisms in Academic Research Platforms

Google Scholar

- **Basic Search:** Like Google's main search engine, Google Scholar employs a simple keyword-based search. It enables researchers to look for conference papers, books, theses, patents, and publications.
- **Advanced Search:** With Google Scholar's sophisticated search function, users can focus their results by entering:
 - **Author:** Looking for papers authored by a certain scholar.
 - **Journal:** Restricting the results to papers that have been published in a specific journal.
 - **Date range:** Results are filtered by year of publication.
 - **Phrase search:** To find specific terms, use quote marks.
- **Citations and Related Articles:** Google Scholar's "Cited by" and "Related articles" links are a crucial component that enable users to track a paper's influence and find related research.

Figure 1: Search Interface of Google scholar

Examples of Using the Features of Google Scholar

- Author-specific search refinement: For example, a researcher looking into the work of "John Smith" can use the author filter to locate all of Smith's publications.
- Citation tracking: In order to ensure that significant papers are not missed and to direct future reading, a researcher might utilize the "Cited by" link to find the most influential papers that have mentioned a seminal piece.

PubMed

- MeSH (Medical Subject Headings): PubMed indexes articles using MeSH, a regulated vocabulary for the life and medical sciences. This enables users to utilize standardized phrases to conduct more precise searches. For instance, the MeSH term "Cardiovascular Diseases" may be the outcome of searching for "heart disease" in PubMed.
- Advance Search Builder: Users can search by field (such as author, title, abstract), date range, research type, and more with PubMed's advanced search builder. You can use filters to limit search results to particular kinds of articles (e.g., reviews, clinical trials, meta-analyses).
- Clinical Queries: To assist readers in concentrating on evidence-based medical literature, PubMed has specific filters for clinical research, including "clinical study," "systematic review," and "meta-analysis."
- Text Mining and Abstract Search: Users can also search within abstracts, full-text, and citations using PubMed's search engine, which is particularly helpful for systematic reviews.

Figure 2: Search Interface of PubMed

Examples of Leveraging PubMed Features

Using MeSH terms: To guarantee that results are consistent and encompass all pertinent papers, including those that may use different language, a researcher studying Alzheimer's illness could use MeSH phrases like "Alzheimer Disease."

Clinical Queries: The "Clinical Queries" filter for systematic reviews or meta-analyses might help a doctor find the greatest evidence when searching for the newest treatment procedures.

JSTOR

- **Advanced Search:** Researchers can search by a number of parameters, including title, author, abstract, subject, and publication date, using JSTOR's advanced search option. By sorting results by content type (e.g., books, papers, reviews, reports), researchers can improve their findings.
- Researchers can search for specific phrases or terms within the body of an article by using full-text search, which makes it easier to locate exact information within publications.
- **Subject Collections:** By classifying content into subject-specific collections, JSTOR enables users to narrow down their search results to certain fields (e.g., literature, art, social sciences, and humanities).
- **Citation & Export Tools:** To manage references in formats such as MLA, APA, and Chicago style, JSTOR offers citation export tools. Users can also check and monitor citation metrics for specific publications.

Figure 3: Search Interface of JSTOR

Examples of Leveraging JSTOR Features

- **Subject Collections:** To filter out irrelevant results from other disciplines and limit their search to solely pertinent items from history journals, a history researcher can utilize the "History" subject collection.
- **Full-Text Search:** To gain a deeper understanding of a certain theory or framework, a researcher can utilize the full-text search feature to find every instance of that term in a publication.

Dimensions AI

- **Advanced Search Features:** Dimensions AI provides robust search features that let users look for information in a variety of areas, such as grants, patents, clinical trials, journals, and financing information. As a result, it is a thorough instrument for multidisciplinary research that covers everything from academic publications to the administrative and financial facets of research.
- **Semantic Search:** Dimensions AI makes use of a semantic search engine that comprehends the context and meaning of search queries in addition to looking for specific terms. This makes it possible for scholars to locate pertinent articles even when the text doesn't contain the exact keyword.

- Citation Graphs and Metrics: Dimensions AI offers a visual citation graph that illustrates the relationships between articles based on citations, which can assist researchers in monitoring the evolution and impact of concepts over time.
- Filters & Facets: Users can narrow down search results by subject area, date range, publication type (such as books, reports, or articles), and more.

Figure 4: Search Interface of Dimensions AI

Examples of Leveraging Dimensions AI Features

- Semantic Search: Even if an article doesn't specifically contain the search word "machine learning," a researcher looking into "machine learning in healthcare" might utilize semantic search to identify relevant work by finding publications that examine the topic in a broad way.
- Citation Graphs: By following the citation trail, a researcher can find the most influential papers and utilize the citation graph to identify important studies that have influenced the field when investigating the evolution of a specific medical treatment.

LISA (Library and Information Science Abstracts)

- Thesaurus of Controlled Vocabulary: To aid improve search efficiency and guarantee more precise results, LISA employs a controlled vocabulary comprising subject headings (such as Library Science, Information Technology, and Bibliometrics). For extremely specialized or esoteric topics, the thesaurus's ability to search using standardized phrases and concepts is quite helpful.
- Abstract Search: Researchers who want to learn more about a paper's scope and topic without reading the complete text can benefit from LISA's abstract search feature.
- Advance Filters: To ensure highly customized results, LISA offers sophisticated filters that let users search by publication type (such as journals, conference proceedings, reports), language, and publication date.

Figure 5: Search Interface of LISA

(Reference: *Search interface of library and information science abstract (LISA)*. (n.d.). OER Commons. <https://oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/123355/overview>)

Examples of Leveraging LISA Features

- **Controlled Vocabulary Search:** To identify papers that utilize the same standardized language, a researcher looking into digital libraries might use the thesaurus to search using particular terms like "digital library development" or "information retrieval systems".
- **Abstract Search:** A researcher can swiftly look through article abstracts to determine a paper's relevance by concentrating on studies whose methods or conclusions match their own areas of interest.

DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals)

Open Access Filter: DOAJ is committed to making open-access journals accessible. This implies that every paper listed in DOAJ's index is openly available, giving readers access to a wide variety of research that is not protected by paywalls.

Journal-Level Search: Researchers can utilize DOAJ's journal-level search function to find entire journals that are devoted to a specific area, such as open-access journals in education or public health.

Advanced Search Features: By selecting an article type, subject area, language, publisher, and publication date, researchers can refine their findings. These criteria assist in focusing searches on the most pertinent open-access publications.

DOAJ Citation Analysis: By offering journal citation metrics, the platform assists scholars in identifying prestigious journals within a particular topic.

Figure 6: Search Interface of DOAJ

Examples of Leveraging DOAJ Features

Filtering by Open Access: A researcher can make sure that all of their sources are open access by using DOAJ's criteria to find freely accessible articles.

Journal-Level Search: To ensure they find a complete collection of publications for their topic, researchers who are especially interested in environmental science can utilize the journal-level search to uncover open-access journals that are dedicated to this field.

OATD (Open Access Theses and Dissertations)

- **Thesis and Dissertation-Focused Search:** OATD is an organization that focuses in making open-access theses and dissertations from universities worldwide accessible. The website is a specialist resource for postgraduate work since it compiles research from numerous universities and sources.
- **Advanced Search Filters:** Users can filter results using OATD's advanced search tool by using criteria like:
 - **Keywords:** Look for particular terms in theses and dissertations' titles, abstracts, or entire texts.
 - **Institution:** Limit the results to theses from certain academic institutions or universities.
 - **Degree Level:** Researchers seeking particular degrees of academic study will find the ability to filter by degree type (e.g., MA, MSc, PhD) particularly helpful.
 - **Date Range:** To locate the most recent work or follow the evolution of a topic over time, filter results by the year of publication.

- **Metadata and Full Text Access:** To facilitate scholars' access to the entire work, a large number of the documents on OATD are either full-text or accessible through links to institutional repositories.

Figure 7 : Search Interface of OATD

Examples of Leveraging OATD Features

- **Institution-Specific Search:** To locate dissertations and theses from universities renowned for their contributions to educational research (e.g., Harvard, Stanford), a researcher interested in comparative studies in education might filter by institution.
- **Degree-Level Search:** To ensure the depth and rigor characteristic of doctorate-level study, a researcher concentrating on environmental science doctoral research can filter results to access only PhD theses.
- **Recent Research:** To make sure they are looking at the most recent research, a user researching new advances in artificial intelligence can narrow down their search to theses published in the last five years by using the date range filter.

CORE (Comprehensive Open-Access Repository)

- **Advanced Search Features:** CORE has a sophisticated search function with a number of filters, such as:
 - **Keywords:** For more complicated queries, keywords enable searching by certain words, phrases, or Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT).
 - **Full Text:** Search results are of higher quality when users are able to look for terms in the complete text of documents rather than just the metadata (title, abstract, etc.).
 - **Document Type:** To concentrate on particular types of scholarly work, researchers might filter by document type (such as article, thesis, or conference paper).
 - **Author and Publisher Search:** To locate particular works or identify important contributors in a field of study, search by author or publisher.

- Year and Language: In order to assist users in selecting research in their favourite languages and concentrating on the most current and pertinent research, CORE additionally provides filters for publication year and language.
- Citation Metrics and Linkage: CORE helps academics find important papers in their field by providing citation data for a large number of articles. In order to provide a more comprehensive view of the scholarly discourse surrounding a subject, the platform additionally connects similar works.

Figure 8: Search Interface of CORE

Examples of Leveraging CORE Features

- Boolean Search and Full-Text Filtering: To ensure they access in-depth research and articles that are directly related to their topic, a researcher interested in the effects of climate change on agriculture can use Boolean operators (such as climate change AND agriculture) to filter results to only display full-text documents.
- Author Search for Tracking Influential Scholars: To locate all of the open-access articles by an influential figure in the field, a machine learning researcher could search by author (for example, "Andrew Ng").
- Citation Tracking for High-Impact Studies: By using citation data provided by CORE, a researcher can identify seminal papers in a topic and explore the network of citations to track the development of a research idea.

Comparison Table of Different Databases

Database Name	Primary Search Mechanisms	Unique Search Features	Search Algorithms	Content Focus	Strengths	Weaknesses
Google Scholar	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Citation searching	Citation linking, Related articles, Author profiles	Relevance ranking, Citation analysis	Multidisciplinary	Broad coverage, Citation-based search, Author profiles	Potential for irrelevant results, Limited to scholarly content only
PubMed	Keyword search, Boolean operators, MeSH terms, Citation search	MeSH terms (Medical Subject Headings), Clinical queries	Relevance ranking, Term matching (MeSH)	Biomedical, Life Sciences	Extensive biomedical coverage, Use of MeSH terms for precision	Limited to life sciences, may miss non-MeSH content
JSTOR	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Citation searching	Subject filters, Access to full-text for certain content	Relevance ranking, Citation analysis	Humanities, Social Sciences	High-quality journal articles, Historical archives	Subscription required, Limited to certain disciplines
Dimensions AI	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Citation search, Faceted search	Semantic search, Citation graphs, Grants, Patents, Clinical trials	Semantic search, Citation graphing	Multidisciplinary, Interdisciplinary	Comprehensive search across multiple sources, Citation graphing	Limited access to full-text for some results, Paid features
LISA	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Subject headings	Controlled vocabulary, Thesaurus for Library & Information Science	Relevance ranking, Subject-specific filtering	Library & Information Science	Specialized content, Use of standardized subject terms (Thesaurus)	Niche content, Limited to LIS field
DOAJ	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Faceted search	Open access filter, Journal-level search	Relevance ranking	Open access, Multidisciplinary	Focus on open access, Global repository of free content	Limited coverage of non-open access content
OATD	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Faceted search	Institution, Degree level, Date range filters	Relevance ranking	Theses, Dissertations	Specialization in theses and dissertations, Full-text access	Limited to postgraduate research, smaller database

Database Name	Primary Search Mechanisms	Unique Search Features	Search Algorithms	Content Focus	Strengths	Weaknesses
CORE	Keyword search, Boolean operators, Full-text search, Citation search	Full-text search, Citation metrics, Related paper linking	Relevance ranking, Citation analysis	Open access, Multidisciplinary	Access to millions of open access papers, Citation data and links	Quality of full-text access can vary, Some content not available

References

- Google Scholar. (n.d.). *Advanced search*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from https://scholar.google.com/advanced_scholar_search
- Google Scholar. (n.d.). *How Google Scholar works*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://scholar.google.com/intl/en/scholar/about.html>
- National Library of Medicine. (n.d.). *Search strategies: PubMed User Guide*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/help/>
- National Library of Medicine. (2024). *MeSH® (Medical Subject Headings)*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>
- JSTOR. (n.d.). *Search tips*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5325/jstor.terms>
- JSTOR. (2023). *JSTOR search guide*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://www.jstor.org/librarians/guides>
- Dimensions. (2024). *Advanced search in Dimensions*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://www.dimensions.ai/>
- Dimensions. (2024). *Citation graph and search mechanisms*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://www.dimensions.ai/resources>
- ProQuest. (2024). *LISA - Library & Information Science Abstracts search guide*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://search.proquest.com/lisa/>
- *Search interface of library and information science abstract (LISA)*. (n.d.). OER Commons. <https://oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/123355/overview>
- Directory of Open Access Journals. (2024). *Search strategies and features in DOAJ*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://doaj.org/>
- Directory of Open Access Journals. (n.d.). *Search DOAJ by subject or journal*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://doaj.org/search>
- OATD. (n.d.). *Advanced search features in OATD*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://oatd.org/>
- OATD. (2024). *OATD search guide*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://oatd.org/oatd/search/>
- CORE. (2024). *CORE search functions and mechanisms*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://core.ac.uk/>
- CORE. (n.d.). *Advanced search in CORE: Tips and tricks*. Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://core.ac.uk/services/advanced-search>
- Biswas, S., & Chakraborty, S. (2024). Search mechanisms of Dimensions.ai. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14313582>